

Association between radiation dose, thyroid hormone, and IQ levels in children exposed to radiation in utero after the Chernobyl accident

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Abstract

Few studies have explored the effects of in utero radiation exposure on human health and cognition and none have taken into account thyroid hormone levels (T3), which have shown to affect cognitive performance. We investigated mechanisms of possible radiation effects on IQ in two cohorts of 250 persons each: exposed in utero after the Chernobyl accident: a “higher exposure group (HEG)”, whose mothers resided in more heavily contaminated territories at the time of the Chernobyl accident, and a “lesser exposure group (LEG)” whose mothers resided in less contaminated areas.

The dataset included information on estimated prenatal thyroid radiation dose, gestation week at the time of the accident (ATA); thyroid hormones: T3 (triiodothyronine) and T4 (thyroxine) levels measured at age 11-12 years and general IQ measured at three time points: $t1$: 6-7 years old; $t2$: 11-12 years old and $t3$: 15-16 years old. Descriptive and inference analyses were used to explore the dynamic of changes through time and the associations between key variables at the three time points.

Estimated radiation doses to the thyroid gland were substantially higher in the HEG than in the LEG (mean 391 vs 25 mGy respectively). Significant differences in thyroid hormones levels were observed between the two groups, with lower values in T3 (higher in T4) in the LEG. At $t1$, the general IQ, as well as verbal and non-verbal IQ scores, were lower in the HEG than in the LEG.

In the HEG, analyses adjusting simultaneously for radiation dose, gestational week ATA and T3 levels suggest that all three variables are associated with IQ, with the latter being highest among those exposed later during gestation and decreasing with increasing level of dose and of T3. No significant association was observed between IQ and T4 levels. No effect of exposure on IQ was seen in the LEG.

Further investigation of this hypothesis will be important to understand the relation between in utero exposure radiation dose to thyroid, thyroid hormone levels and IQ, taking into account effects of potential confounding factors (physiological stress, maternal anxiety related evacuation).

Key words: in utero exposure, thyroid doses, Chernobyl accident, thyroid hormones, IQ

Highlights:

1. We followed up persons exposed in utero to radiation from the Chernobyl accident

2. Among the most highly exposed, IQ was higher among those exposed later during gestation
4. Among the most highly exposed, IQ also decreased with increasing level of dose and of T3
5. No such relation was seen in those with lower exposure
6. Our study provides insights into the possible relation between prenatal radiation dose and IQ and the factors which may modify it

Introduction

Radiation exposure in utero may occur from medical diagnostic examinations (X-ray, CT scans, etc.). Previous studies suggested that low fetal doses (less than 100 mGy) do not increase fetal malformation, while doses from 200 to 500 mGy may be related to IQ reduction, and doses greater than 500 mGy may provoke growth retardation and CNS damage (Timins 2001). However, at low doses, the evidence is too limited to draw conclusions. Given the ubiquity of radiation exposure in our general environment it is important to continue studying the possible risks from radiation exposure in utero (Sreetharan et al. 2017). In the meantime, it is important to ensure strict adherence to Radiation Protection guidelines for exposure of the fetus, with diagnostic and therapeutic procedures undertaken in pregnant women only when the benefits outweigh the possible negative effects (Brent 2015), and keeping exposure as low as reasonably achievable (ALARA) (McCullough 2008).

More than 35 years have passed since the accident at the Chernobyl nuclear power plant (NPP) in Ukraine occurred on 26 April 1986, leading to substantial releases of radioactive materials into the atmosphere. Belarus, which is located close to the Chernobyl NPP, was one of the countries most contaminated by radioactive fallout. As a result, the population in nearby areas received high radiation doses to the thyroid gland from intake of locally produced cow's milk, dairy products and leafy vegetables contaminated with Iodine-131 (^{131}I) (Igumnov and Drozdovitch 2000), leading to increased risk of thyroid cancer and thyroid disorders among those exposed at young ages (Cardis et al. 2005).

Iodine is crucial for fetal neurodevelopment (Lucas et al. 1996; Kapoor et al. 2015; Velasco et al. 2018), and for this reason it is recommended that pregnant women take stable iodine as a nutritional supplement in case of iodine deficiency (Donnay et al. 2014). Since the fetal thyroid is not fully developed until 18-20 weeks of pregnancy (Demeneix 2019), the fetus relies on the maternal supply of thyroid hormones for regulating vital processes in early brain development (Korevaar et al. 2016). An association between low neonatal triiodothyronine (T3) concentration and lower IQ scores (in particular verbal scale) has been reported at 7.5-8 years

in children born before term (Lucas et al. 1996). However, in adults, higher T3 score within normal ranges has been reported to be associated with poorer performance of executive functions and processing speed (Grigorova and Sherwin 2012).

Concerning ionizing radiation exposure, studies of the atomic bomb (A-bomb) survivors showed that the periods 8–15 weeks and 16–25 weeks of gestation were critical stages for the neocortex and total brain development. In these studies, prenatal radiation exposure was related to lower IQ, smaller head size, mild mental retardation, as well as poorer neuromuscular performance (grip strength and fine motor coordination required in repetitive action) (Otake and Schull 1993; Yoshimaru et al. 1995; Otake and Schull 1998; Schull and Otake 1999).

There is scarce information from other groups of children exposed in utero. A study of 342 children exposed in utero (born between September 1986 and February 1987 and exposed in the first weeks and months of gestation, a critical for organogenesis period) to fallout from the Chernobyl accident in the most contaminated regions of Belarus, Ukraine and Russia, showed an increase in microcephaly, Down's syndrome and congenital defects of the central nervous system at age of two to three years (Terestchenko, N. Ya et al. 1993). One third of this group did not reach appropriate psychomotor development for their age (Terestchenko et al. 1993). These negative consequences may be due to prenatal exposure of the thyroid gland to ^{131}I , since ^{131}I was the largest contributor to the thyroid dose in these regions. Radiation dose to the thyroid gland may also lead to alteration of other endocrine glands - the hypophysis and hypothalamus. This, in turn, might result in delays in central nervous system maturation, low psychological and emotional development and other mental disorders (Lyaginskaya et al. 1992).

A cross-sectional study performed in Norway on adolescents exposed in utero to Chernobyl fallout (84 exposed with estimated mean external dose of 0.9 mSv, 94 matched non-exposed controls with mean external dose of 0.01 mSv) found lower IQ scores overall in the exposed compared to the control group (significant for verbal IQ) (Heiervang et al. 2010). This study also found that participants exposed after 16 weeks of gestation (after the sensitive time window period for neurodevelopment) performed as well in IQ tests as participants from non-exposed group.

Results are also available of another cross sectional study of in utero exposed children, including 544 children born between April 26, 1986 and February 1987 in the radioactive-contaminated regions of the Ukraine and 759 children, born in the same period in less contaminated areas. This study showed a higher prevalence of specific developmental,

borderline emotional and behavioral disorders at age 6-7 years in those resided in the more contaminated area (Nyagu et al. 1996). However, the authors report that other, non-radiological, confounding factors, such as parent's mental health, family socioeconomic status and prenatal complications could explain these findings (Nyagu et al. 1996). Other psychological stress factors including forced migration, adaptation to new conditions, sometimes with difficulties in integration and psychosocial isolation of children (Langmeier and Matejcek 1984) may also trigger oxidative processes similar to those caused by ionizing radiation (Cwikel et al. 2010).

We previously reported on a cohort of 500 Belarussian children exposed in utero to fallout from the Chernobyl accident – including 250 children whose mothers resided in more heavily contaminated after the Chernobyl accident territories and 250 from lesser contaminated areas. We found that general IQ at age 6-7 years was lower in the higher exposed group (HEG) than in the lesser exposed group (LEG) (Igumnov and Drozdovitch 2000; Igumnov and Lapanau 2015; Liutsko et al. 2018). The goals of the current investigation in the same cohort were: 1) to study differences in thyroid hormones (T3 and T4) between the HEG and LEG; 2) to study differences in IQ scores (general, as well as verbal and non-verbal) between the HEG and LEG at three follow-up time points, and 3) to evaluate the relationship between IQ scores (general, verbal and non-verbal), thyroid doses and thyroid hormone levels in both groups separately.

Methods

Participants

The HEG cohort consisted of 250 Belarussian persons (127 males and 123 females) exposed in utero to fallout from the Chernobyl accident. They were born between 26 April 1986 and 1 March 1987 to mothers resided in areas with ^{137}Cs ground deposition densities from 100 to 15,400 kBq m⁻². The LEG cohort included 250 persons, matched on age and sex who were born to mothers who resided permanently in areas with ^{137}Cs ground deposition densities ranging from 0.2 to 200 kBq m⁻². The parents of the LEG's subjects had no professional contact with sources of ionizing radiation. There were no differences between the two groups in socio-economic status of parents - most of them were farmers and industrial workers.

The study was approved by the Ethical committee of the 2nd Meeting of the Belarussian Psychotherapeutic Association dated 19th of June 2003 with accordance of the Helsinki Declaration.

Measurements of IQ and thyroids hormones

The intellectual quotient (IQ) was evaluated using the Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children – WISC- III UK (Wechsler 1991) at three time points: *t1* (6-7 years old); *t2* (11-12 years old); and *t3* (15-16 years old). Participation rate was 100% at *t1* and *t2*, and 99% at *t3*. The functional state of the thyroid gland was assessed at *t2* in the radioimmune laboratory of the Republican Dispensary of Radiation Medicine of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Belarus based on the level of thyroxine (T4) and triiodothyronine (T3) in blood plasma by radioimmune method. The reference values obtained in this laboratory, taking into account the correction by the "percentile method" corresponding to the age group (11-12 years old), were 1.17-2.70 nmol/L for T3 and 62-141 nmol/L for T4.

Dosimetry

Thyroid doses to the fetuses were estimated based on the mothers' individual thyroid dose estimates and a transfer coefficient to fetus taking into account the gestational period at the time of exposure (Zvonova and Balonov 1993). Thyroid doses derived from ¹³¹I intake were reconstructed from ¹³¹I thyroid activity measurement (available for 25 mothers from the HEG), or estimated based on information about the mother's lifestyle after the accident, applying an ¹³¹I environmental transfer model adapted to Belarussian conditions (Drozdovitch et al. 1997; Arefieva, Z.S. et al. 1998; Drozdovitch et al. 2015). Uncertainty in estimated individual thyroid doses were estimated by Drozdovitch (Drozdovitch et al. 2015; Drozdovitch et al. 2020) taking into account the dose estimation method used (direct thyroid activity measurements or model calculations). Information on the mother's lifestyle was obtained by questionnaires during the *t1* and consisted in 1) consumption rates of foodstuffs most important for iodine intake: fresh milk and milk products; 2) origin of consumed alimentary products; 3) interruption of consumption of locally produced products; 4) residence ATA; 5) migration during April-June 1986; and 6) iodine prophylaxis.

Statistical analysis

We conducted descriptive analyses of the distribution of gestational age, dose, T3 and T4 levels between the two study groups. We used linear regression to evaluate the relation between IQ scores (general, as well as verbal and non-verbal separately), thyroid dose, gestational week and thyroid hormone levels at the three follow-up time points: *t1* (6-7 years old); *t2* (11-12 years old), and *t3* (15-16 years old). Analyses were conducted separately in the higher and lesser exposed groups. Due to the high correlation (collinearity) between T3 and T4 the

regression models were run separately. All analyses were adjusted for sex and conducted in STATA v15.

Results

Results of the descriptive analyses are shown in Table 1, overall and by exposure group. Both groups had similar gestation age ATA and sex distributions due to the matching. The frequency of preterm births (gestation period less than 260 days) was similar in both groups: 18 in the HEG vs. 16 in the LEG (not shown). No case with extremely low body weight (less than 1000 grams) was observed in either group. Gestational age ATA ranged up to 39 weeks in the HEG and up to 37 weeks in the LEG, respectively.

As expected, the doses to the thyroid gland differed substantially between the two groups: mean dose of 390 mGy and 25 mGy in the HEG and LEG, respectively. T3 level was statistically significantly higher (and T4 was statistically significantly lower) in the HEG than that in the LEG (Table 1). IQ (general as well as both verbal and non-verbal) at *t1* was statistically significantly lower in the HEG than in the LEG but not at the other time points (Table 1).

Strong correlations were observed between IQ levels measured at the three follow-up time points ($r=0.86-0.98$, $P<.001$) within both groups (not shown). No correlation between T3 and T4 ($r=0.12$, $P>.05$) was observed in the LEG, but a moderate correlation ($r=0.50$, $P<.001$) was found in the HEG. A low correlation was also seen between gestational week and dose ($r=0.23$, $P<.001$) for the whole group; with a slightly higher correlation in the in HEG ($r=0.37$, $P<.001$) than the LEG ($r=0.30$, $P<.001$). No significant association was found between T3 or T4 levels and thyroid doses within either the LEG or the HEG.

Table 2 gives the results of the linear regression analysis of general IQ level and T3 hormone at the three follow-up time points. In the HEG, dose was significantly negatively related to general IQ at all three follow up time points with a coefficient that ranged for -0.02 for a dose of 1 mGy at *t1* to -0.04 at *t3*. Gestational age ATA was positively associated with IQ at *t1*; the strength of this association appeared to decrease in later follow-ups. Increasing T3 was associated with lower IQ at all time points when adjusting for dose and gestational period though the association was not statistically significant at *t1*.

The effects of dose and gestational age were similar in the model adjusted for T4 instead of T3 but T4 was not strongly associated with IQ at any time point. No association was observed between IQ and any of the variables in the model in the LEG apart from a positive association

with sex at $t3$ in the model adjusted for T4. The effects of gestational age and of sex on IQ were, however, statistically compatible in the LEG and HEG and at the different time points.

Results of analyses of verbal (IQV) and non-verbal IQ (IQNV) are shown in Tables A1 and A2 (IQV) of the Annex. Results were consistent with those for general IQ (Table 2 and 3), with both IQV and IQNV negatively associated with thyroid dose in the HEG in all follow-up time points, though the association was of marginal significance at $t1$.

In the LEG, sex was positively associated with non-verbal IQ at all time points in the model adjusted for T3, suggesting slightly higher non-verbal performance in boys (Table A2).

Discussion

Our study is one of the few longitudinal studies to date allowing the simultaneous evaluation of the impact of radiation dose, gestational age at exposure and thyroid hormone levels on IQ at different ages.

T3 concentrations were slightly, but statistically significantly, elevated (though within the normal ranges) in the HEG compared to the LEG. These differences may not be due to the mediation effects of radiation, since no correlation between thyroid doses and thyroid hormones levels were observed within each group. Instead, they may reflect the joint (synergetic or independent) effects of both thyroid hormone levels (T3 specifically) and thyroid doses.

Our results may also reflect the effects of unmeasured confounders. We did not have information on emotional state in our cohorts, in particular differences in levels of anxiety and depression, which can also impact IQ scores (Grigorova and Sherwin 2012). As reported by other studies, however, it is likely that mothers who resided in highly contaminated territories experienced psychological stress, including forced migration and adaptation to new conditions, which could have affected their children. In addition, children whose parents were evacuated or relocated from highly contaminated territories might have experienced difficulties in integration and psychosocial isolation (Langmeier and Matejcek, 1984) as they were born in evacuated families and may have experienced bullying for “being contaminated” (Maeda et al. 2019; Oe et al. 2019). These non-radiation effects – stress, anxiety, etc. - related to the nuclear accident, post-accidental period or to other environmental factors may also trigger oxidative stress similar to those caused by ionizing radiation (Cwikel et al. 2010). These psychological factors – likely not experienced – or to a lesser extent - by the LEG – may have

influenced both T3 levels and final IQ scores in the HEG in our study and explain the different relations between IQ and dose and T3 observed between the two groups.

Increasing T3 appeared to be associated with decreasing IQ (general and verbal and non-verbal) even after adjustment for dose and gestational age ATA at all time points (not statistically significantly so at *t1* or *t2*) in the HEG (but not in the LEG), with an estimated reduction of 2.8-3.9 IQ points in general IQ score per nmol/L of T3 (see Table 2). This observation is consistent with that of Grigorova and Sherwin (Grigorova and Sherwin 2012) in adults, who reported that higher T3 concentration, within the normal ranges, was associated with processing speed and executive functions that might also influence IQ scores. The lack of such an effect in the LEG might reflect, as mentioned above, the influence of other factors, in particular psychological stress.

Although general IQ was lower in the HEG compared to the LEG, only at *t1* was the difference statistically significant and the difference in mean values in general IQ scores between the two groups decreased with time, from about 2.5 IQ points at *t1* to 1.1 IQ point at *t3* (see Table 1). Results were similar for verbal and non-verbal scores, unlike previous results from Norway which suggested a reduction only in the verbal component (Heiervang et al. 2010). Differences with that study may be due to radiation dose levels, which were much lower in the Norwegian study.

No association was observed between IQ scores, thyroid hormone levels and thyroid radiation doses in the LEG. We cannot conclude that such associations do not exist as they would need to be tested in a study with a larger sample size. The negative association of thyroid doses with IQ scores found here in the HEG should be also examined to see if there is any possible threshold for the cognitive effects of radiation.

Our study has several strengths, including the assessment of individual radiation doses, the evaluation of thyroid hormone levels, and the assessment of IQ at three time points, up to 15-16 years after exposure. This allowed us to study the possible relationship between IQ scores, thyroid radiation doses and thyroid hormone levels. We were able to explore simultaneously the association between IQ and thyroid dose, T3 and T4, while adjusting for gestational week ATA and sex. We were also able to examine these associations separately in the HEG and LEG. In the HEG, radiation dose, gestational age at the time of the exposure and T3 appeared to be determinants of IQ (general as well as verbal and non-verbal) at all observations time points (*t1*, *t2* and *t3*), although these associations did not always reach statistical significance.

There were no such associations in the LEG, suggesting that the effect of T3 in the HEG might be complementary to radiation exposure, possibly related to psychological effects such as stress related to evacuation and relocation in the HEG.

Our study also, has a number of limitations, including:

- 1) Relatively small sample size of the HEG, even though we included the majority of persons exposed in utero accident and evacuated to Minsk. Analyses of other in utero exposed groups from highly contaminated areas of Ukraine and Belarus (Nyagu et al. 1996; Yauseyenko et al. 2020) would be useful to confirm or inform our results.
- 2) Relatively small sample size in the LEG: while we attempted to evaluate the impact of dose and T3 and T4 following low doses of radiation, any effect at these doses is expected to be small and therefore would require much larger population to adequately address the problem.
- 3) The reliability of retrospective information on individual behaviour and diet at and around the time of exposure, collected during a personal interview a long time after exposure, could be subject to some recall error and affect both the dose estimates (Drozdovitch et al. 2016) and the subsequent effect estimates. However, if the errors are not differential with respect to IQ level, the impact of such errors is likely to bias effect estimates towards the null, thus further reducing the power to identify an effect.
- 4) The thyroid hormone levels were measured only once, in the beginning of the adolescent period, t_2 , which is 11-12 years after exposure, not reflecting levels in early life and over time.
- 5) We were not able to estimate the significance of other socio-economical and psychological effects (stress due to migration and adaptation to a new place) that could contribute to the final IQ scores in the HEG.

Nevertheless, we feel that our study provides important insights into the possible role of prenatal radiation exposure as well thyroid hormones with respect to neurodevelopment and cognitive function later in life.

Conclusions

Our study results suggest that the associations between IQ with radiation thyroid dose in utero exposure to radiation (T3) and T3 thyroid hormone levels were shown only HEG only. Further

investigation of this hypothesis, taking into account effects of potential confounding factors (physiological stress, maternal anxiety related evacuation) will be important to verify our results and further our understanding of the relation between in utero exposure radiation dose to thyroid, thyroid hormone levels and IQ.

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Table 1. Descriptive statistics of main variables

Group Variables / Statistics	Lower Exposed Group			Higher Exposed Group		
	M (Med)	min	max	M (Med)	min	max
Gestation week ATA	16.7 (16)	0	37	18.2 (17)	0	39
Thyroid dose	25.4 (10)	0	290	391 (225)***	0	4070
T3	2.4 (2.4)	1.07	4.8	2.5 (2.5)*	1.11	4
T4	131.1 (132.5)	60.3	265.5	127.8 (126)***	69	285
IQ_t1	92.1	47	122	89.6**	51	122
IQ_t2	95.8	48	128	94.3	55	128
IQ_t3	99.6	53	130	98.5	57	133
IQV_t1	91.0	54	123	88.7**	48	128
IQNV_t1	94.1	46	118	91.6**	54	120
IQV_t2	94.6	55	129	93.3	52	134
IQNV_t2	97.5	48	125	96.0	57	122
IQV_t3	98.4	59	131	97.7	54	138
IQNV_t3	101.3	53	129	100.0	60	127

Legend: ATA: at time of accident; IQV – verbal part of IQ, IQNV – non-verbal part of IQ; Med – median; for IQ test: *t1* – 6-7 years old; *t2* – 11-12 years old; *t3* – 15-16 years old; thyroid hormones T3 and T4 units were nmol/L; dose – mGy; in **bold** the variables that differ in both groups at statistically significant level as per bivariate chi-square tests: *(P<.05), **(P<.01), ***(P<.001).

Table 2. Regression analysis for IQ by dose and T3 in each of the study groups

IQ_t1						
Group	Lesser exposed group			Higher Exposed Group		
Variables/Statistics	Coef.	95% CI		Coef.	95% CI	
Thyroid dose	0.03	-0.34	0.40	-0.02	-0.05	-0.003
T3	0.56	-3.20	4.33	-2.78	-6.11	0.53
Gestation week ATA	-0.06	-0.18	0.06	0.13	0.01	0.25
Sex	1.99	-0.64	4.63	0.35	-2.22	2.93
IQ_t2						
Group	Lesser exposed group			Higher Exposed Group		
Variables/Statistics	Coef.	95% CI		Coef.	95% CI	
Thyroid dose	-0.01	-0.39	0.37	-0.03	-0.05	-0.007
T3	0.28	-3.63	4.19	-3.35	-6.77	0.06
Gestation week ATA	-0.06	-0.18	0.06	0.10	-0.01	0.22
Sex	1.98	-0.75	4.71	-0.08	<-0.01	2.57
IQ_t3						
Group	Lesser exposed group			Higher Exposed Group		
Variables/Statistics	Coef.	95% CI		Coef.	95% CI	
Thyroid dose	0.00	-0.39	0.39	-0.04	-0.06	-0.01
T3	-0.19	-4.19	3.80	-3.90	-7.36	-0.48
Gestation week ATA	-0.05	-0.18	0.06	0.08	-0.03	0.21
Sex	2.51	-0.28	5.31	0.13	-2.57	2.83

Legend: In **bold** – statistically significant differences; and **bold with cursive** – marginally significant differences (p<=0.1).

The variable “sex” was coded as: 1 – Female, 2 – Male, thus, a coefficient above 1 means a stronger relation in boys compared to girls. Thyroid hormones T3 unit were nmol/L; dose – mGy.

ANNEX. Complementary analyses: Regression analysis for verbal and non-verbal parts of IQ

Table A1. Regression of the verbal part of IQ (IQV) test on T3 and dose in three time points:

IQ_t1						
Group	Lesser Exposed Group			Higher Exposed Group		
Variables/Statistics	Coef.	95% CI		Coef.	95% CI	
Thyroid dose	0.11	-0.25	0.47	-0.02	-0.05	-0.005
T3	2.04	-1.63	5.73	-2.69	-5.85	0.47
Gestation week ATA	-0.04	-0.64	0.07	0.13	0.02	0.25
Sex	0.76	-1.80	3.34	0.49	-1.96	2.95
IQ_t2						
Group	Lesser Exposed Group			Higher Exposed Group		
Variables/Statistics	Coef.	95% CI		Coef.	95% CI	
Thyroid dose	0.09	-0.28	0.47	-0.03	-0.05	-0.007
T3	1.80	-2.03	5.64	-3.13	-6.58	0.19
Gestation week ATA	-0.04	-0.16	0.08	0.13	0.01	0.26
Sex	0.56	-2.11	3.25	-0.09	-2.72	2.53
IQ_t3						
Group	Lesser Exposed Group			Higher Exposed Group		
Variables/Statistics	Coef.	95% CI		Coef.	95% CI	
Thyroid dose	0.10	-0.29	0.49	-0.04	-0.06	-0.01
T3	1.21	-2.76	5.19	-3.40	-6.86	0.05
Gestation week ATA	-0.06	-0.18	0.06	0.10	-0.01	0.23
Sex	1.21	-1.67	3.90	0.21	-2.50	2.93

Legend: In **bold** – statistically significant differences; and in **bold with cursive** – marginally ones ($p \leq 0.1$). For variable “sex”, the coding was as following one: 1 – F, 2 – M, thus, direct associations, would mean higher trends in boys compared to girls. Thyroid hormones T3 units were nmol/L; dose – mGy.

Table A2. Regression of the non-verbal part of IQ (IQNV) test on T3 and dose in three time points:

IQ_t1						
Group	Lesser Exposed Group			Higher Exposed Group		
Variables/Statistics	Coef.	95% CI		Coef.	95% CI	
Thyroid dose	-0.08	-0.44	0.28	-0.02	-0.04	0.002
T3	-0.85	-4.52	2.80	-3.28	-6.55	-0.01
Gestation week ATA	-0.05	-0.17	0.06	0.09	-0.02	0.21
Sex	3.13	0.56	5.69	0.52	-2.01	3.06
IQ_t2						
Group	Lesser Exposed Group			Higher Exposed Group		
Variables/Statistics	Coef.	95% CI		Coef.	95% CI	
Thyroid dose	-0.10	-0.56	0.21	-0.02	-0.05	-0.004
T3	-1.06	0.07	0.66	-2.93	-6.24	0.37
Gestation week ATA	-0.05	-0.17	0.07	0.06	-0.05	0.17
Sex	3.04	0.37	5.71	-0.28	-2.85	2.28
IQ_t3						
Group	Lesser Exposed Group			Higher Exposed Group		
Variables/Statistics	Coef.	95% CI		Coef.	95% CI	
Thyroid dose	-0.07	-0.45	0.31	-0.03	-0.06	-0.01
T3	-1.27	-5.16	2.62	-3.48	-6.81	-0.15
Gestation week ATA	-0.08	-0.21	0.04	0.05	-0.06	0.16
Sex	3.33	0.60	6.05	-0.16	-2.78	2.44

Legend: In **bold** – statistically significant differences; and in **bold with cursive** – marginally ones ($p \leq 0.1$). For variable “sex”, the coding was as following one: 1 – F, 2 – M, thus, direct associations, would mean higher trends in boys compared to girls. Thyroid hormones T3 units were nmol/L; dose – mGy.